

DATA ENCRYPTION USING BIO MOLECULAR INFORMATION

Behnam Bazli, Mustafa Anil Tuncel and David Llewellyn-Jones

Department of Computing & Mathematical Sciences
Liverpool John Moores University, UK

ABSTRACT

Cryptography is a field, which makes the transmitted message unreadable to unauthorised users. In this work we take inspiration from DNA encryption schemes and use of biological alphabets to manipulate information by employing the DNA sequence reaction, to autonomously make a copy of its threads as an extended encryption key. Information is converted from plain text to several formats and then follows the stages of protein formation from DNA sequences to generate an extended key using chemical property and attributes to be used in encryption mechanism. This technique will enhance the security of the encryption mechanism by substitution, manipulation, and complexity. Furthermore this technique can be used in many applications of information and communication systems as well as adding more complexity to existing encryption algorithms.

KEYWORDS

DNA Sequence, Encryption; security, Bioinformatics & Communication

1. INTRODUCTION

Process of converting messages from plain text to cipher text is called cryptography. Cryptography is a technique of achieving security for communications by encoding plain text messages to make it unreadable[1]. Encryption is a useful tool in protecting confidentiality and integrity of information. It is simply a technique for hiding the true meaning of the information from unauthorised users. The worst case of an attack within communication is complete control of the encryption system by illegitimate users. This happens by accessing the encryption algorithm to decrypt the data and access sensitive information. Cryptography relies on uncertainty in encoding the message to its cipher format. Redundancy in the known human languages [2] and limitations and flaws of the cryptography methods make them vulnerable especially to frequency analysis based attacks. A cryptanalyst can apply a frequency analysis based attack with the most repetitive letters, 'E' and 'I', to extract the message. With the entire precaution, security policy, and the complex algorithm, one thing is certain regarding the cryptosystems; if the attacker accesses the key that is used to encrypt the message, the message becomes readable.

DNA based bimolecular cryptography design is a technique that uses the huge parallel processing capabilities of bio molecular computation which converts short messages from hexadecimal and ASCII forms and then back to encrypt and decrypt the information. This has been used on different applications, but we consider using this technique to safeguard sensitive information with the addition of the key generation technique from the bio-molecular properties of the DNA sequences.

DNA computing started by Adleman [3] trying to solve a small instance of the Hamiltonian path problem using parallel computing. DNA is considered as a medium for ultra-compact

information storage, exceeding capability of conventional electronic media. A few grams of DNA may hold all data stored in the digital mediums in the world.[4]

The unique property of DNA encoding is used for computations, improve the security and encryption and to mitigate the flaws of the current security mechanism. In this work we take inspiration from DNA to manipulate information by employing the DNA sequence reactions, to autonomously make a copy of its threads with a high fidelity for comparison. Furthermore we use chemical properties of the sequences as an indexing keys to authenticate the communications and hide information from exploitation techniques used by intruders specially frequency analysis based attacks. The DNA sequences and different stages from aligning the sequences with other biological languages and process of protein construction from the source property can be used to manipulate and encode data with inspiration from such methods.

Forming protein from DNA sequences goes through a composite process, adding different catalysts and enzymes to the sequences while maintaining the integrity and validity of the process. The process is a complex and difficult, which gives the DNA based cryptography an advantage over other public key based cryptography methods. In other words, the security of such an algorithm relies on the difficulty of solving problems. We take this into account to go through current security methods and encryption algorithms to propose a novel algorithm to enhance the security and complexity of an encryption mechanism.

2. BIMOLECULAR COMPUTATION

The DNA is a sequence of nucleotides. The exact sequences of the nucleotides determine the code of each gene. DNA sequences represent biological information such as skin colour, weight, nose shape, eye, and hair as well as other features[5]. A DNA sequence is of a long molecule with four bases called nucleotides Adenine (A), Guanine (G), and Cytosine (C) and Thymine (T). DNA Sequences is succession of those letters that indicate order of nucleotides. Because of weak forces between the sequences, they pair as A-T and G-C. They form a chain around each other in the opposite direction to form a double helix. Although there are only four bases in the sequence, their arrangement in the long double helix is random and can be billions of combination of codons. This is how everybody in the world has different DNA. Such a capacity has created a field to mathematicians and cryptanalysts to explore the capability and functionality of the DNA sequences and bio molecular computation. DNA computing and its capability is used for parallel computing. The potential of DNA allows the researchers to solve numerous computational problems by parallel processing.

2.1. DNA Encryption

DNA stands for Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid, a genetic material in human organs. The information in DNA is stored as code of four chemical substances namely; Adenine A, Cytosine C, Guanine G, and Thymine T. The order and sequences of these bases provide information about individuals such as peoples' name formed with alphabetical appearance[6]. This provides capacity and potential for many mathematical and statistical solutions dealing with data and provides naming, addressing and other functionality. The computational capability of DNA has been found by Leonard M Adleman [3]. DNA based bio molecular cryptography design is a library of one-time-pads assembled secretly in the arrangement of DNA strands which is used to encrypt or decrypt short messages[4].

The computation carried out using a DNA sequence is called DNA Computing. Diverse problems with significant storage capacity have been solved using parallel computing

methods[8]. Watson [7] has combined traditional cryptography with DNA sequences to introduce hybrid security. The chains in a DNA have phosphate of one nucleotide and sugar of the next nucleotide to form a strand. DNA consists of two chains twisted around and form double strand helix. A and T are bond together while C and G bond in an opposite chain. Design information of DNA is transmitted to new cells during development and growth using complimentary pairing. The complimentary of the strands enables information to be replicated autonomously using a synthesizing template[1]. These complimentary strands are triplets of codons of nucleotides bases to form strands like figure 1;

A G G – C T C – A A G _ T C C _ T A G
T C C _ C A G _ T T C _ A G G _ A T C

Figure 1. DNA Sequences

DNA strands are mapped to numbers and alphabetical letters and other attributes and widely used for encoding and decoding as well as digital storing of data. Information encryption using DNA sequences can be used on the communication encryption methods, especially the ones in need of a robust data encryption scheme to challenge unauthorised access.

DNA translation, transcription

When two DNA strands are separated by an enzyme, a single strand messenger RNA, complementary to DNA strand, is formed by mapping from DNA sequences, which consist of A, T, C, G, to complementary RNA sequences, which consist of U, A, G, C. These process non-coding segments, called introns in DNA sequences, are removed by splicing and remaining segments that encode information for protein synthesis, called exons, are assembled in mRNA [10].

Figure 2. Translation Process from DNA to RNA& Protein [10]

DNA and RNA both share common codons; A, G, C. DNA has an additional T codon whereas RNA has an additional U codon. Both these additional codons are used to form proteins. Figure 2 illustrates the simple concept of how three bases in DNA copied to mRNA by replacing T with U. The combination and sequence of the three letter codons of mRNA determines the order of the amino acids on the diagram. Figure 3 shows example of a protein construction through transcription and translation, which converts to amino acids to construct a protein cell;

Figure 3. Transcription Process from RNA to Amino Acid [10]

Transcription is the synthesis of RNA from a DNA template as illustrated in figure 3. Only one strand of DNA is copied. A single gene may be transcribed thousands of times. After transcription, the DNA strands re-join to form amino acids and subsequently protein.

2.2. DNA Mutation

Genetic information is encoded by the order of DNA nucleotides. A mutation is a change in genetic information [7]. DNA mutation involves insertion, deletion or substitution. There are some instances in DNA codons represents same amino acids as shown in table 1.

Table1. Amino Acid representation of RNA codons

First Base	Second Base								Third base
	U		C		A		G		
U	UUU	Phe	UCU	Ser	UAU	Tyr	UGU	Cys	U
	UUC	Phe	UCC	Ser	UAC	Tyr	UGC	Cys	C
	UUA	Leu	UCA	Ser	UAA	Stop	UGA	Stop	A
	UUG	Leu	UCG	Ser	UAG	Stop	UGG	Trp	G
C	CUU	Leu	CCU	Pro	CAU	His	CGU	Arg	U
	CUC	Leu	CCC	Pro	CAC	His	CGC	Arg	C
	CUA	Leu	CCA	Pro	CAA	Gin	CGA	Arg	A
	CUG	Leu	CCG	Pro	CAG	Gin	CGG	Arg	G
A	AUU	Ile	ACU	Thr	AAU	Asn	AGU	Ser	U
	AUC	Ile	ACC	Thr	AAC	Asn	AGC	Ser	C
	AUA	Ile	ACA	Thr	AAA	Lys	AGA	Arg	A
	AUG	Start	ACG	Thr	AAG	Lys	AGG	Arg	G
G	GUU	Val	GCU	Ala	GAU	Asp	GGU	Gly	U
	GUC	Val	GCC	Ala	GAC	Asp	GGC	Gly	C
	GUA	Val	GCA	Ala	GAA	Glu	GGA	Gly	A
	GUG	Val	GCG	Ala	GAG	Glu	GGG	Gly	G

GUU, GUC, GUA and GUG within the table above all represent the amino acid ‘Valine’ with representing three letters ‘Val’. Substitution of the last letter will not make any changes to genetic information or in the protein chain. However changing the first letter of GUU to A will would create ‘Isoleucine’. This would result in malfunctioning of the represented protein. This

chemical reaction of DNA sequences sometimes has no effects, but this can be valuable and help some problem theories.

When the sequence increases drastically, space complexity seems to be the major concern of dealing with a DNA searching system. Each of the DNA bases is converted to binary value before the matching process[9]. This enables to insert the one-time-pad or 'Exclusive-OR' algorithm in DNA sequences introduced by Gehani et al. If there is any error, a DNA strand is broken into segments and rearranges itself. In some cases the process involves deletion or insertion of some parts of DNA to form a correct codon base to recover from the error. These steps are taken to repair the damage to DNA, called mutation. DNA alignment is a fundamental comparison method to find common patterns between sequences, identify important regions, which consist of matching characters between two sequences or more, and positioning them correctly in a column. A count of the matching characters results in a measure of similarity between the sequences.[10]

3. RELATED WORKS

3.1. Data Encryption standard (DES)

DES is one of the modern cryptography algorithms to protect data. It is a symmetric encryption system, which uses 64-bit blocks. The algorithm uses combination, substitution and permutations between the text to be encoded and a key is generated. There is only 56 useful bits, which they are used for key generation leading to 2^{56} different keys. Security of the DES algorithm relies on complexity of encryption key. With the powerful processors running on different machines they can find the possible key in a considerable amount of time [15].

First, the 128-bit key is partitioned into eight 16-bit sub blocks, which are then directly used as the first eight key sub blocks. The 128-bit key is then intermittently shifted to the left by 25 positions, after which, the resulting 128-bit block is again partitioned into eight 16-bit sub-blocks to be directly used as the next eight key sub-blocks. The cyclic shift procedure described above is repeated until all of the required 52 16-bit key sub blocks have been generated[1].

3.2. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)

AES uses 128 bit block, a robust replacement for DES and supports larger size of blocks which is suitable to a wide range of systems, from smart cards with tiny memory capacities to large multiprocessor mainframe systems [16]. This type of algorithm supposed to protect the confidential but unclassified information against attacks, except brute-force attacks. Brute-force attack is process of systematic checking all possible key combinations until the correct key is found[11].

With the capability of new 128 bit AES key, it will take one billion years to break the key using a super computer, making AES secure against brute force attacks. However, public knowledge of the AES algorithm makes it vulnerable to known and unknown attacks. Practically this algorithm is not feasible to use on classified communications.

3.3. Asymmetric Encryption with DNA Technology

In DNA –Public Key Cryptography (PKC), there are two types of keys[12]; first one to be used for encryption and second one to create signature. Original message is encrypted using a public

key and is decrypted by only those who own a private key. To create a signature a sender signs the message using a private key, which is de-coded by only the corresponding public key. The keys in this method are biological molecules. The security is relied on the difficult biological problems. DNA PKC is immune from Quantum computer based attacks. Since it is impossible to replicate the cypher text, cloning can be prevented.

3.4. One-Time-Pad using DNA

Gehani et all [4] introduced one-time-pads based on DNA to propose two encryption methods. One method uses substitution technique to convert DNA sequences to cipher format using a pre-defined mapping table. The introduced key in one-time-pad is only used once making it impossible to break. The one-time-pad is stored in a large size library of codes, which is used once, and then discarded after that. Considering the limitation of this method, it is resilient to brute-force attacks and frequency analysis attacks, but as the library itself needs robust security, it is vulnerable to targeted attacks. If unauthorised users access the database, then the integrity and confidentiality of all communications can be compromised. The one-time-pad algorithm uses 'Exclusive-OR' operation of plain code and cipher key sequence. Exclusive-OR operation is impractical for DNA sequences. But Gehani et al. established one-time-pads by creating word pairs. All the algorithms for DNA encryption use pair-wise mapping to codon. It uses a substitution method using libraries of distinct pads, each of them, which define specific pair-wise mapping keys. The method employs vast parallelism capability of DNA sequences and possible solutions represented by DNA strands.

3.5. Primer

In this method a primer is designed to be transmitted between parties, which represent block of text. Data is converted to hexadecimal and then binary formats. Using DNA templates the binary formats then converted to DNA sequences. By applying the special function of primers to Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) amplification, the primers and coding mode are used as the key of the scheme[13]. The original and converted sequences of the DNA look entirely different with the PCR digital coding technique. Complimentary strands, normally attach separated pairs of DNA to each other a short string of nucleotides, called enzymes. It continues adding the complimentary codons until DNA strands are completed. This is explained in the DNA replication technique is this paper.

Sender and receiver create blocks of messages and choose a representation character, or words, for each block. Sharing the primer by both, the receiver will use the table to read the corresponding message. Senders and receivers only communicate using primers, therefore the original message never transmitted over the public channel. This is secure because if the primer is found, the original message will not be obtained and revealed. Although this is a secure method to communicate sensitive information, several primers are required to fulfil communication demand. Also both parties should have access and agree on the original message and corresponding primer.

4. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The proposed algorithm consists of several stages of conversions using different conversion tables as stated in figure 4. Some attributes and chemical properties of DNA sequences are inserted in this paper to explore the capabilities of such components on DNA encryption and to add complexity. Detailed descriptions and representing tables included within this section;

Any information stored in a computer such as text and images, is in form of binary, which represented by 0 and 1. Using the DNA and RNA alphabets explained in section 2, we now can form a table to map these representations to binary bits as demonstrated in table 2. The 3 codons DNA sequences also mapped to alphanumeric values as demonstrated in table 3. These alphanumeric representations can be used for insertion or substitution as described in section 2 in this paper to form an encryption key or to insert in the encryption process.

Table 2. Binary to DNA Conversion

S.No.	Bit1	Bit 2	DNA	RNA
1	0	0	A	A
2	0	1	C	C
3	1	0	G	G
4	1	1	T	U

Data entry is converted to ASCII format. After, the ASCII format is converted to DNA sequences, then RNA sequences using a key generated from corresponding lookup tables of the sequences to be encrypted and sent over the public channel. A secret key is generated using amino acid properties of the RNA sequences to be converted back to binary format cipher text.

It is not possible to translate the 16 bases RNA to amino acid, as the amino acid sequences are three letters long. The example above shows 16 nucleotides, which will make 5 amino acids with A, C, and U bases. We have remainder of U at the end of 15 letters long sequence. We can add a complimentary letter like the one in chemical mechanism to insert messages to DNA strands. However, the reverse operation of the DNA to RNA conversion will reveal the strand, therefore, exposing the message. Since every alphabet has representing RNA and DNA codons, to fill the gap at the end of the string we assume representation of the codon letter as alphabet and insert 2 or 3-letter codon. If a sequence ended with T, then the three letter codon, TTT will replace it. Since the insertion is done at the end of the string to make the sequence with three bases, therefore, the reverse operation will return the original message. This is exactly what happens in chemical processing of DNA replication when extra base pairs are inserted into a new place on the DNA sequences.

One can use this method to insert a message primer as explained in section 3; this method also can be used to insert digital signature or digital certificate within a file or image to be sent over public channel.

After the DNA sequences is converted to RNA format, a secret key is generated from the chemical properties of the associated amino acids from table 3 and is used to convert the RNA format to binary sequences by substitution of the letters. The final Binary format is adding more complexity to the algorithm and more confusion to the cryptanalyst who will try to convert the binary to ASCII format. Since the DNA and RNA sequences as well as secret key generated from the amino acids are not easy to guess on the binary format. The cipher text then converted to binary format. The reverse operation is performed to decrypt the cipher text. Figure 4 illustrates the different operations and stages of conversion of messages to cipher format using associated tables. Although the final conversion of the cipher text to binary format will confuse any cryptanalyst, but the main strength of the proposed algorithm is the choice of the secret key from the amino acid properties of associated codons and sequences. Here are the stages of encryption;

1. Text Input to be encrypted (Message)
2. Message converted to ASCII Format
3. ASCII format then converted to Binary
4. Binary bits converted to DNA sequences using Table 2
5. DNA format converted to RNA
6. RNA format of the DNA is added with represented letter from corresponding amino acid table to the end of sequence blocks (Table 1)
7. Paired RNA format is converted back to binary using table 2
8. Match the size of the binary with the original binary format using compression algorithm
9. Final Binary format is sent over public channel

The size of the final binary format of the cipher text is matched with the original one, diverting suspicion. As stated in figure 4, the reverse operation of the encryption will reveal the plain text message transmitted over public channel;

Figure 4. Encryption and Decryption

Figure 5 demonstrates the conversion process implemented and displayed in GUI format. The word 'hello' is inserted for encryption, and the final binary format of the message is displayed. Since the intermediate conversion tables and using a different format of data is included in the

process, an authorised decryption process is very difficult if not impossible without knowing the reverse process. As shown in the figure 4, the keys selected from lookup tables are used to accomplish the reverse operation. An adversary should have all the tables available as well as knowing all the conversion and insertion stages to retrieve the encrypted message.

Figure 5. Encryption Process Using the Conversion Steps

4. Look up Table and key Generation

When DNA is transcribed, RNA is synthesized using this code. The RNA is a complimentary copy of one strand of the DNA. The RNA leaves the nucleus and in the cytoplasm it is translated into a protein. Each set of three contiguous RNA nucleotides codes for a single amino acid, and the protein is made of a chain of amino acids hooked to one another. Each set of three nucleotides in the DNA eventually codes for one amino acid in the final protein that is made from a given gene. The nucleotides and amino acids are not similar chemically, and it is the protein synthesis machinery of the cell that is needed to translate one code into the other. Table 3 is alteration of look up table from [1] which maps numeric and alphabetic values to codon triplets which is used as a look up table. Since this is widely used in almost all of the DNA-based cryptography [14] and easy to utilise by attackers, we use further secret key generation technique to extend the complexity. This technique will allocate a key from chemical properties of the DNA sequences and is obtained by both parties. If the message is decrypted and revealed by an attacker, the true meaning of the message will not be readable without this secret key. As the key choice and its method of use is decided on a prior agreement between two parties and never transmitted over public channel, it will be impossible to access. Other attributed and properties from the amino acids and chemical properties of the DNA strand can be used for data manipulation and substitution. This provides various choices for parties to agree on and use for data encoding, data encryption as well as data hiding.

Table 3. Map 3 Letter Codons to English Alphabets

Codon	English	Codon	English	Codon	English	Codon	English
AAA	a	CAA	q	GAA	G	TAA	W
AAC	b	CAC	r	GAC	H	TAC	X
AAG	c	CAC	s	GAG	I	TAG	Y
AAT	d	CAT	t	GAT	J	TAT	Z
ACA	e	CCA	u	GCA	K	TCA	1
ACC	f	CCC	v	GCC	L	TCC	2
ACG	g	CCG	w	GCG	M	TCG	3
ACT	h	CCT	x	GCT	N	TCT	4
AGA	i	CGA	y	GGA	O	TGA	5
AGC	j	CGC	z	GGC	P	TGC	6
AGG	k	CGG	A	GGG	Q	TGG	7
AGT	l	CGT	B	GGT	R	TGT	8
ATA	l	CTA	C	GTA	S	TTA	9
ATC	n	CTC	D	GTC	T	TTC	0
ATG	o	CTG	E	GTG	U	TTG	space
ATT	p	CTT	F	GTT	V	TTT	.(period)

There are 500 different types of amino acids. But there are only three bases to encode 20 amino acids [George Gamow biography] by living cells to build protein. A code of 3 nucleotides codes maximum of $4^3 = 64$ amino acids. The process of protein formation from DNA sequences is called transcription and translation as demonstrated on figure 3.

Table 3 demonstrates the information about biological properties of the chemical attributes of the DNA sequences, which is used for public key generation.

Table 4. Chemical Attributes of Amino Acids

Base	A	G	C	T	U
Name	Threonine	Alanine	Lysine	Valine	Glycine
Formula	$C_4H_9NO_3$	$C_3H_7NO_2$	$C_6H_{14}N_2O_2$	$C_5H_{11}NO_2$	$C_2H_5NO_2$
3 letter Symbol	Thr	Ala	Lys	Val	Gly
PH	5.60	6.00	9.74	6.96	5.97
H	9	7	14	11	5
N	1	1	2	1	1
O	3	2	2	2	2
C	4	3	6	5	2
MW	119	89	146	117	75
Weight	119.12	89.10	146.19	117.15	75.07
Residue Weight	101.11	71.08	128.18	99.13	57.05
Hydro-phobic value	13	41	-23	76	0
Assigned English Letter	C	M	A	O	N
Code Triplet	ACU	GCU	AAA	GUU	GGU

We propose chemical properties of the DNA sequences are used for key generation purposes, which will be autonomously generated for communications encryption. This will enhance the encryption security. There are many other properties and unique attributes of the common amino acids as listed in table 3, which can be used as indexing table to generate a secret key.

This process relies on agreement by both parties in advance on the choice, which provides numerous choices of keys in order to be used for information encoding. This technique can replace many key generation mechanisms used for digital signatures, one-time-pad techniques, and any other techniques that employ DNA sequences for encryption and information hiding purposes.

Table 5: Amino Acid Representation of DNA Codons

DNA Codon	T	C	A	G
T	TTT } Phe TTC } TTA } Leu TTG }	TCT } TCC } Ser TCA } TCG }	TAT } The TAC } TAA } STOP TAG }	TGT } Cys TGC } TGA } STOP TGG } Trp
C	CTT } CTC } Leu CTA } CTG }	CCT } CCC } Pro CCA } CCG }	CAT } His CAC } CAA } Gln CAG }	CGT } CGC } Arg CGA } CGG }
A	AAT } Ile ATC } ATA } ATG } Met	ACT } ACC } Thr ACA } ACG }	AAT } Asn AAC } AAA } Lys AAG }	AGT } Ser AGC } AGA } Arg AGG }
G	GTT } GTC } Val GTA } GTG }	GCT } GCC } Ala GCA } GCG }	GAT } Asp GAC } GAA } Glu GAG }	GGT } GGC } Gly GGA } GGG }

Combining the chemical attributes of the amino acids in table 3, alphabetical representation of codons listed in table 2 and representing amino acids in table 4 can have massive capacity for data manipulation, substitution, and insertion to extended key generation which can be used to encode confidential information sent over public channel.

5. DISCUSSION

The traditional library of code books consists of the large number of one-time-pads. This in turn contributes to a long portion substitution in converting the plain text to DNA sequences making this method of encryption unbreakable, but at the same time inefficient. With an eye on the well-known principle "the security of the crypto scheme is in key management, not secrecy of the algorithm (Kahn, The code breakers)" it is imperative to manage the key generation sensibly, and choose a secret key carefully, rather than designing a robust and complicated algorithm. In [12], authors propose a public encryption key using, generated from cipher texts together with a signature to verify the public key. However, authors consider only quantum-based attacks on the evaluation of the proposed method. Nonetheless, acquisition of the signature physically, poses limitations on the DNA-PKC method. In the proposed algorithm, a message is encrypted through several stages of conversion to different formats with insertion of secret key from a lookup table. This key is generated from the chemical property of the DNA sequences. This will add more complexity and complication to encryption mechanism. The one-time-pad algorithm prevents future penetration and is resilient to frequency analysis based attacks, but the limitation of choice is the real constrain for the algorithm. Numerous communications require several one-time-pads. However, use of random choice from a table which is generated based on the plain text content will be more flexible, efficient. Furthermore, it is hard to access by cryptanalysts that use frequency based attacks. Maintaining and securing a large database with one-time-pads is challenging task. Using the chemical reaction of DNA sequences and forming proteins is a procedure that has engaged many scientists already. Using that procedure and technique in information technology is growing subject for researchers, both in biology and the cryptography.

6. CONCLUSION

Most of the known algorithms for DNA encryption use secret codes from one-time-pads generated from DNA sequences as a secret key to encrypt data. The database consisting of one-time-pads requires robust security policy. Moreover, using complex authentication and access model for one-time-pads may require further processing power. This paper proposes use of chemical properties of the DNA sequences of the cipher text to encrypt data over the public channel to add key extension and complexity to the encryption algorithm. This technique will add uncertainty to the key and message exploitation. Furthermore, if the cipher text is accessed and content is revealed, the true meaning of the message will not be revealed without the key. This technique will enhance the security of the encryptions and encryption algorithms.

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AUTHORS

Behnam Bazli is a PhD Candidate and researcher at Protect Lab within Liverpool John Moores University, UK. His research interests include Ubiquitous Systems Security, Forensic Computing, Internet of Things and P2P Systems.

Mustafa Anil Tuncel is a Software Engineer and researcher from Atilim University in Ankara, Turkey. He is currently visiting Liverpool John Moores University and involved in various research projects. His research interests include Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligent and Game Technology.

David Llewellyn-Jones is Reader in Computer Security within Liverpool John Moores University, UK. His Research interests include distributed Network security, Forensic Computing and Machine Learning.